

An Improved Measurement Method for Radio Frequency Exposure from 5G NR Base Stations

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Abstract— In this publication, an improved measurement method is proposed for the quantification of the radio frequency exposure from 5G NR base stations in sub-6 GHz frequency range. The method is based on the code selective measurements of all resource elements in the resource grid and enables an estimation of the exposure at maximum data transmission. In particular, it allows the quantification of the ratio between traffic resource elements and synchronization resource elements. The use of this method is presented in this publication and some preliminary results of the laboratory measurements are demonstrated, which were performed using a code selective measuring receiver implementing the proposed method for analyzing the full 5G resource grid.

Index Terms— Base station, downlink, exposure, fifth generation (5G), frequency analysis, New Radio (NR), radio frequency (RF), secondary synchronization symbol (SSS)

I. INTRODUCTION

Emerging mobile communication technologies such as fifth generation New Radio (5G NR) make use of complex, flexible and cooperative usage of available frequency and time domain resources in order to improve the efficiency and to increase the throughput. These complexity and versatility create additional difficulty for the quantification of RF exposure. High dynamic allocation of the resource elements (RE) in the resource grid, and the possible difference in the power levels of the synchronization signals and the traffic signals make it difficult to reliably estimate the maximum exposure. The exact location of the measurement point with respect to the antenna (i.e., the measurement angle) is also important since the antenna diagrams of the synchronization signals and of the traffic signals might also differ significantly. Therefore, improved measurement methods that could be used to validate the existing ones is of great interest. With such an improved method, the focus would not be on the estimation of the actual exposure, which can be obtained using a frequency selective probe, but rather on the estimation of the maximum exposure at maximum traffic and maximum transmit power.

Various examples of the RF exposure measurement methods for 5G NR are present in the literature. Some of these measurements are based on frequency-selective methods (See [1], [2] and [3]) and some are on code selective methods (See [4], [5] and [6]). For the estimation of the maximum exposure, two different approaches are available in the literature. The first one is based on obtaining the full capacity of a 5G base station by triggering traffic in the

direction of the measurement location using an end user equipment (such as a mobile phone) and by artificially generating traffic using a large download file [7] or by employing some specific traffic protocols, such as iPerf mentioned in [8]. The other approach is based on the measurement of the synchronization signals and employing additional extrapolation techniques on these measurements to determine the maximum exposure [9, 10]. A very complete overview of the different evaluation methods is available [11].

The contribution in [1] presents a didactic method to estimate the power of the Secondary Synchronization Symbol (SSS) REs as well as the power of the traffic REs. The benefit of that method is that a good approximation of the RF exposure can be obtained by using simply a professional spectrum analyzer in different steps (including intermediary evaluations and representations), however the application is limited to a bandwidth of 1 MHz. This limitation makes the method in [1] impractical because the total bandwidth of a typical 5G NR transmission could go up to 100 MHz.

In this publication, we propose an improved measurement method based on first using a code selective device measuring the full bandwidth of the 5G-NR signal and then applying the adapted evaluation techniques. The proposed method is currently applicable to RF exposure measurements in the sub-6 GHz band and it is based on the real-time decoding of the full resource grid. This improved method can produce a high number of data, about 1 million values per 10 ms. For this reason, a statistical analysis in terms of power histogram is proposed to allow a nearly real-time treatment of the information. This histogram representing the measurement values is then used to extract the RF powers of the traffic REs and ideally does not require any prior knowledge on SSS.

For the purpose of this study, and in close discussion with a code selective field probe manufacturer, the algorithm has been implemented on a commercially available 5G NR measuring receiver. This device has been used in this study to perform preliminary measurements of a 5G NR signal generator in a laboratory environment where the benefit and the functionality of the method could be illustrated.

This paper is organized as follows: In Section II, some ground information on 5G NR downlink transmission is given, the challenge in the measurements of the whole

resource grid is emphasized and the proposed measurement method is presented in detail. In Section III, the measurements performed with the 5G NR measuring receiver in a laboratory environment are illustrated and discussed for different traffic conditions and 5G NR configurations. Finally, the summary of the findings, the conclusions and the future work are given in Section IV.

II. IMPROVED MEASUREMENT METHOD FOR RF EXPOSURE IN SUB-6 GHZ BAND

The conformity of the base stations is often determined based on the electric field strength at the highest transmit power, and for the highest possible speech and data traffic conditions. One of the methods used in this context is based on the extrapolation of the electric field measurements of the secondary synchronization signal (SSS) [12]. The difference between traffic and synchronization antenna diagrams are obtained from the antenna specification. This approach can be improved if more information between the synchronization REs and the traffic REs is available.

In this proposed method, the entire resource grid is measured, meaning that the power of each RE in the resource grid is quantified individually. Since the bandwidth of the resource grid can reach about 100 MHz and the duration of a radio frame is 10 ms, this defines a time-frequency product for the of $10^6 \text{ s Hz} = 10^6$. The time-frequency product of one RE is equal to 10^6 s Hz in 5G NR, thus meaning that up to about 1 million of values are measured every 10 ms, or up to 100 million values per second. The treatment and the recording of this high number of values overpass the capacity of most commercially available computers.

Therefore, we propose a statistical representation of 1 million values per frame into a power histogram. Bins of predefined power steps are defined from -150 dBm to 0 dBm. The power step size can be chosen as 0.1 dB, 0.2 dB, or 0.5 dB. This means that depending on the power step, 1 million values (real numbers) of one frame of the resource grid can be summarized into 1500 integers, 750 integers or 300 integers, respectively. As an example, the histogram representation of a sample measurement is depicted in Fig. 1. The signal was produced by a 5G NR signal generator, where the power of traffic and synchronization signals can be selected freely. In Fig. 1, the peaks can be identified as the background noise (peak on the left) as the traffic signal (peak in the middle), and as the SSS signal (small peak on the right). The x-axis is given in terms of power in dBm.

It is important to note that since 1 million values are treated for the duration of every frame (10 ms) and represented with 1500 integers, it is not possible to record every consecutive frame. Depending on the bin size of the statistical evaluation and on the bandwidth of the 5G NR signal, the analysis of the measured frame can last from 0.2 s to 4 s.

In this publication, the application of the proposed method is illustrated only for FR1.

Fig. 1. Sample histogram output. System noise, traffic and SSS peaks are shown.

With this evaluation technique, the quantification of the resource elements is performed individually and over the full bandwidth of the signal. This is a major difference to [1] is that in [1], the measurements are performed over a bandwidth of 1 MHz, thus taking only about 1% of the possible bandwidth of the 5G-NR signal into account. With the proposed method here, the case of the maximum bandwidth of 100 MHz in FR1 can be measured and important information regarding the exposure can be obtained. Moreover, since the measurements are performed using a frequency selective instrument in [1], the power per RE is obtained as an averaged RE power over the measured bandwidth. On the other hand, with the method proposed in this publication, an individual power measurement for a selected radio frame is obtained.

III. MEASUREMENTS IN LABORATORY ENVIRONMENT

The proposed method has been implemented on the commercial 5G measuring receiver Deviser EM860 EMF Analyzer with the software option "5G NR Statistics" [13]. Using this receiver, the measurement of the full resource grid and its evaluation were performed here in a conducted environment in order to validate the measuring features. Some of the measurements reported here are also obtained using the option "5G NR EMF" of the same receiver: it is the case for the precise code selective measurement of the incident SSS power for each SS/PBCH block as well as the quadratic sum as required by [12].

The setup for the on-the-bench measurements is depicted in Fig. 2 and the list of the equipment used in the setup is given in Table I.

TABLE I. EQUIPMENT FOR MEASUREMENTS IN LABORATORY ENVIRONMENT

Equipment	Brand and Model
Signal Generator	Rohde & Schwarz SMW200A with 5G option
Cable	Huber+Suhner Sucotest 1 m
5G NR Receiver	Deviser EM860 with 5G NR Statistics option

Fig. 2. Measurement setup in the laboratory environment

A. Case Definitions

In order to assess the capability and the limitations of the method and the implementation on the 5G measuring receiver, seven cases are defined as given in Table II. The cases were defined to cover different frequencies, numerologies and traffic situations. This preliminary study has been realized with a signal bandwidth of 10 MHz. Relative power of the SSS RE compared to the Traffic RE has been varied from -6 dB to +6 dB in steps of 3 dB as shown in Table II.

TABLE II. CASE DEFINITIONS FOR MEASUREMENTS IN LABORATORY

Case	Carrier Frequency (MHz)	Numerology	SSS Power (dBm)	Traffic Power relative to SSS (dB)
1	1500	0	-53.6	-6
2	1500	0	-55.1	-3
3	1500	0	-60.5	3
4	1500	0	-63.4	6
5	3500	1	-49.1	-10
6	3500	1	-49.8	-6
7	3500	1	-57.7	6

For each case as reported in Table II, three different traffic conditions have been simulated: namely, 10% traffic, 20% traffic and 50% traffic. The resource grids for each situation for numerology 1 are depicted from Fig. 3 to Fig. 5.

The resource grids for numerology 0 are not illustrated here because of its similarity to numerology 1 and the limited space in this publication. The only difference is the number of SSB blocks, which is 4 for numerology 0.

Fig. 3. Resource Grid for one radio frame, numerology 1 and 10% traffic (The darkest areas are SSB blocks, the dark grey areas correspond to the traffic and the light grey areas are unused resource elements)

Fig. 4. Resource Grid for one radio frame, numerology 1 and 20% traffic (The darkest areas are SSB blocks, the dark grey areas correspond to the traffic and the light grey areas are unused resource elements)

Fig. 5. Resource Grid for one radio frame, numerology 1 and 50% traffic (The darkest areas are SSB blocks, the dark grey areas correspond to the traffic and the light grey areas are unused resource elements)

B. Measurement Results

The measurement results for the scenarios defined in Table IV are depicted from Fig. 6 to Fig. 12. Since the system noise was around -93 dBm, it was removed from these figures to illustrate the signals of interest more clearly.

Fig. 6. Power Histogram for Case 1

Fig. 10. Power Histogram for Case 5

Fig. 7. Power Histogram for Case 2

Fig. 11. Power Histogram for Case 6

Fig. 8. Power Histogram for Case 3

Fig. 12. Power Histogram for Case 7

Fig. 9. Power Histogram for Case 4

C. Discussion of Measurement Results

The measurement results show that the method provides the expected information on the downlink transmission of a 5G base station. In particular, the power difference between the traffic REs (peaks with changing amplitudes) and the SSS REs (overlapping peaks of smaller amplitude) are in agreement with the case definitions for all traffic situations. The same observation is performed for the traffic peaks, which can be identified by their traffic-dependent amplitudes. As a numerical example, the measured power of SSS for Case 1 is -53.5 dBm whereas the measured powers of traffic REs for all traffic conditions are around -59.5 dBm, which yields

the expected difference of 6.0 dB. Moreover, the measured SSS power (-53.5 dBm) is also matching well with the generator setup given for Case 1 in Table II.

Furthermore, the number of REs is also increasing proportionally with the incident traffic in all cases as expected. For example, in Case 3, the number of REs corresponding to 10% Traffic is around 750 REs, whereas, this number is doubled to 1500 REs for 20% Traffic case and quintupled to 3750 REs for 50% Traffic, as expected.

It is also important to note that with the increasing numerology (i.e., subcarrier spacing), the observed peaks are becoming wider in the histogram (cases 5 to 7). This change arises from the broadband characteristics of the transmission medium (i.e., the cable). For numerology 1 (i.e., subcarrier spacing of 30 kHz), REs have higher bandwidth with respect to numerology 0, therefore, the broadband fading is more apparent. For this reason, REs from the same signal (SSS or traffic) have more dispersed power levels, yielding in broader peaks in the histogram.

The results of the conducted tests show that the measurements in the laboratory environment provide accurate results for different traffic cases. The traffic density, the power of the traffic REs and also the power of SSS REs can be measured simultaneously with this method in a measurement duration less than a second.

IV. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, an improved measurement method and its implementation on a commercial product is introduced to measure the power of 5G NR downlink traffic signals. The method is based on the statistical analysis of the resource elements of the full resource grid and can be used to identify the power of SSS REs and of the traffic resource elements.

The method was validated in a laboratory environment. Under such well-controlled conditions, it was found to be perfectly working for different numerologies and frequency ranges. Different traffic densities and power scenario could be measured and quantified correctly.

This contribution shows that the method constitutes a promising tool in order to quantify the RF exposure from 5G base stations including traffic and SSS signals, and also to understand their operating conditions.

As for the future work, detailed over-the-air measurements will be conducted in order to correlate the measurements with the operating mode of the base station.

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